

ON A RELATION BETWEEN THE RIEMANN ZETA FUNCTION AND THE STIRLING NUMBERS

Hiroataka Sato

*Japanese Language Center for International Students, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, 3-11-1,
Asahi-cho, Fuchu, Tokyo, 183-8534, Japan*
htsato@tufs.ac.jp

Received: 12/17/07, Accepted: 11/3/08, Published: 12/3/08

Abstract

Let $\zeta(z)$ be the Riemann zeta function and $s(k, n)$ the Stirling numbers of the first kind. Shen proved the identity $\zeta(n+1) = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{s(k, n)}{k \cdot k!}$ ($1 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}$). We give a short proof by elementary methods.

1. The Result

Let $\zeta(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{-z}$ be the Riemann zeta function, and let $s(k, n)$ denote the Stirling numbers of the first kind, which are defined by

$$s(0, 0) = 1, \quad s(k, 0) = s(0, n) = 0 \quad (k \neq 0, n \neq 0), \quad (1)$$

$$s(k+1, n+1) = s(k, n) + k \cdot s(k, n+1) \quad (k \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{Z}). \quad (2)$$

Shen [2] proved the following identity, which shows an interesting relation between $\zeta(n)$ and $s(k, n)$ by using Gauss's summation theorem of the hypergeometric series:

$$\zeta(n+1) = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{s(k, n)}{k \cdot k!} \quad (1 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}). \quad (3)$$

In this paper we give a short proof of (3) by elementary methods.

First we show the outline of the proof. We denote

$$(k)_{-n} = \frac{1}{k(k+1)(k+2) \cdots (k+n-1)} \quad (1 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}, 1 \leq k \in \mathbb{Z})$$

and put $\xi(n) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (k)_{-n}$. Then we have

$$\xi(n+1) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \{ (k)_{-n} - (k+1)_{-n} \} = \frac{1}{n \cdot n!}. \quad (4)$$

Proposition. For $1 \leq x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $0 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}$ we have

$$x^{-(n+1)} = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} s(k, n) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)}. \tag{5}$$

By this proposition we have

$$\zeta(n + 1) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} m^{-(n+1)} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} s(k, n) \cdot (m)_{-(k+1)}.$$

Since it is a convergent series with positive terms, we can change the order of summation. Noting (4), we obtain

$$\zeta(n + 1) = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} s(k, n) \xi(k + 1) = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{s(k, n)}{k \cdot k!}.$$

Now we prove the proposition above. We need the following result [1, Section 54, p. 160].

Lemma. For fixed $1 \leq k \in \mathbb{Z}$, we have $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{s(N, k)}{N!}$.

We prove (5) by induction on n . The case $n = 0$, which is $x^{-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} s(k, 0) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)}$, follows from (1) and the definition of $(x)_{-k}$. Now let N be a sufficiently large integer. From (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=n}^N s(k, n) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} &= \sum_{k=n}^N (s(k + 1, n + 1) - k \cdot s(k, n + 1)) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} \\ &= \sum_{k=n}^N s(k + 1, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} - \sum_{k=n}^N k \cdot s(k, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} \\ &= \sum_{k=n}^N s(k + 1, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+2)} \cdot (x + k + 1) - \sum_{k=n}^N k \cdot s(k, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} \\ &= \sum_{k=n+1}^{N+1} s(k, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} \cdot (x + k) - \sum_{k=n+1}^N k \cdot s(k, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} \end{aligned}$$

(Note $s(n, n + 1) = 0$.)

$$= x \cdot \sum_{k=n+1}^{N+1} s(k, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)} + s(N + 1, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(N+2)} \cdot (N + 1).$$

Noting $x \geq 1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} s(N + 1, n + 1) \cdot (x)_{-(N+2)} \cdot (N + 1) &\leq s(N + 1, n + 1) \cdot \frac{N + 1}{1 \cdot 2 \cdots (N + 2)} \\ &= \frac{s(N + 1, n + 1)}{(N + 1)!} \cdot \frac{N + 1}{N + 2}, \end{aligned}$$

which tends to 0 as $N \rightarrow \infty$ because of the lemma above. Therefore as $N \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain by the induction assumption

$$x^{-(n+1)} = x \cdot \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} s(k, n+1) \cdot (x)_{-(k+1)}.$$

Hence we have complete the proof of (5).

Remark. Let $S(n, k)$ be the Stirling number of the second kind and denote $(x)_n = x(x - 1) \cdots (x - n + 1)$ for $1 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Equation (5) can be viewed as the negative n case of the well-known identity

$$x^n = \sum_{k=0}^n S(n, k) \cdot (x)_k \quad (0 \leq n \in \mathbb{Z}).$$

References

[1] C. Jordan, *Calculus of Finite Differences*, 3rd ed., Chelsea, 1965.
 [2] L. C. Shen, Remarks on some integrals and series involving the Stirling numbers and $\zeta(n)$, *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.* **347** (1995), 1391-1399.